

Effects of Organizational Culture on Employee Productivity in State Department of Livestock Nakuru County-Kenya

Dr. Charles Mulandi Zakayo

Senior Lecture, School of Business and Economics,
Kabarak University, Kenya

1. ABSTRACT

Organizational culture is a system of shared beliefs and attitudes that develop within an organization and guides the behavior of its members. It consists of norms, values and rules of conduct in an organization as well as management styles, priorities, beliefs and interpersonal behaviors. All these have impact on organization's productivity. Organizational culture exists in all organizations and affects the morals and motivation of organizational members. This study intended to analyze the effects of organizational culture on employee productivity in the department of livestock in Nakuru County and it was guided by the following specific objectives:- to establish the effect of management style on employee's productivity in state department of livestock in Nakuru County, to assess the effect of motivation on employee productivity and to establish the effect of staff training on employee productivity. The study used descriptive research design. The target population was 124. The sample of the study was 62 respondents consisting of employees and management. Data was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively by the help of SPSS program.

Keyword- Organizational culture, Employee's productivity, motivation, staff training and management style.

2. INTRODUCTION

People are the best asset in any organization. Employees translate organizational goals into reality. According to Armstrong (2004), employees' productivity refers to the degree of accomplishment of the task that make-up an employee's job. Managers and supervisors should ensure the jobs of their employees have all the vital components that are crucial for enhancing employees' welfare and

productivity. Good management enhances employee productivity. Organizational structure and policies should be well designed to promote employees welfare and improve their working conditions. Goals and objectives should be clear. Qualified and competent employees should be hired, placed on the right jobs and given required training. Clear job description, fair appraisal system and fair rewarding system enhance productivity (Armstrong 2006). Sense of purpose, feeling of personal impact and overall trust among employees and between managers and employees promotes productivity.

They way structures and systems are organized and function in an organization creates an organizational culture that can promote or impede employees' productivity. Efforts and expertise is necessary in designing quality organizational structures and systems that promotes employees' welfare (Armstrong, 2006).

Herzberg's theory on motivation states that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors- motivation and hygiene factors respectively. Employee's motivation to work is continually related to satisfaction in the job. Motivating factors are intrinsic to the job but hygiene factors are aspect of working environment such as pay, company policies, supervisory practices and other working conditions (Dickson, 2000).

3. PROFILE OF STATE DEPARTMENT OF LIVESTOCK

Most Kenyan communities have traditionally kept livestock for subsistence, and as a form of insurance against drought. Animals also served other social needs like paying bridal price and traditional ceremonies.

With the arrival of the western culture and gradual interaction with the global economy, livestock trade in Kenya picked more economic importance. The organization of livestock subsector started in 1898 with the creation of the veterinary department headed by the veterinarians in the British Army. In 1987, the department of livestock production was created. Prior to 1980, the livestock sub-sector was under the mandate of the Ministry of Agriculture but thereafter the ministry of livestock development was created.

The existing national livestock department policy was developed in 1980 and its objectives were: to address the high poverty incidence, enhance foreign exchange earnings and food security, to emphasize on sustainable use of environment and provide raw materials for both processing and manufacturing industry.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Achievement of high level employees' productivity in an organization would be crucial for the overall productivity and profitability of an organization. Most organizations have not embraced proper management of human resources in order to achieve high levels of productivity in employees. Organizational culture influences productivity in many ways. Many organizations in public sector have not been able to organize their employees to produce as much as possible and help the organization and individuals accomplish their objectives. This study aimed at assessing the effects of organizational culture on employee productivity in the state department of livestock- Nakuru County.

General objective

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of organizational culture on employees' productivity in the state department of livestock Nakuru County.

Specific Objectives

1. To establish the effect of management style on employee productivity in the state department of livestock Nakuru-Kenya
2. To assess the effects of motivation on employee productivity in the state department of livestock in Nakuru County Kenya.
3. To establish the effect of staff training on employee productivity in the state department of livestock Nakuru County Kenya.

Scope of the study

The research focused on the effects of organizational culture on employees' productivity in the state department of livestock in Nakuru County. It zeroed to management style, motivation and staff training and their effects on employees' productivity.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical reviews

According to Edgar Shein (1992) model of organizational culture, there are mechanisms that direct and indirect influence organizational culture;- Organizational culture is directly influenced by motivation, behavior, status of the staff and opinions. It is also indirectly influenced by management style, mission and vision of a company, rules and regulations, corporate identity rituals and designs.

CHARLES HANDY (1985) MODEL FOR CULTURE

Charles Handy Outlined Four Different Kinds of Culture Which Includes:- power culture, role culture, task culture and person culture. Power culture is where power is held just by a few individuals whose influence is felt in the whole organization.

Role cultures are based on rules. All the staff are expected to know their roles and responsibilities. Power in a role culture is determined by a person's position in the organization hierarchy.

Task culture: this is formed when teams in an organization are formed to address specific problems or project progress. In this culture the task at hand is the most important thing therefore power keeps shifting depending of the mix of the team members and the status of project being handled.

Person culture: this culture has employees who see themselves as unique and superior to the organization and other colleagues and their major purpose is to work.

Deal and Kennedy's (1982) model for organization culture

This culture is based on staff training, feedback and reward after they have done something. Action plans and corrective measures are effective when feedback is provided immediately leading to effectiveness and existence of a constant culture

Deal and Kennedy (1982) outlined four cultures:-

Work-hard, play-hard culture: Here employees need immediate feedback and they have to maintain high levels of energy.

Process culture: This culture has slow feedback and low risk resulting to low stress, slow working, relaxation and security at work and it takes long to find out whether the decision is right or wrong.

Bet-your company: Here, decisions are high risk but employees may wait for long before they know whether their actions are right or wrong.

Tough-guy macho: this culture contains a world of individuals who enjoy risk and who get quick feedback on their decisions. Here employees enjoy excitement and work hard to be stars.

MANAGEMENT STYLE

According to Armstrong (2003) the management style plays a vital role in developing and implementing organizational transition and ensuring that procedures for carrying out change assessment, audits and inspections are implemented. Management styles have the duty of monitoring and evaluating transition and taking corrective actions where necessary. Managers are responsible for ensuring that employees are conscious of the likely changes that may take place within the organization. Manager has two fold, first the employee must know what to do and secondly this knowledge must be translated into action following the transition that has taken place within the organization (Chopra, S, & Clara 2004). Management must ensure that the style it employs complies with laid down working procedures.

Haroold et al (2005) noted that management style has to operate on two fronts regarding how to implement transition measures in the workplace. Making work better for its employees and ensuring appropriate working condition. According to Armstrong (2006) management style of any industry should support the implementation of transition policies, communicate the need for good aligning of change practices, provide a systematic risk assessment, ensure that the change policies are investigated thoroughly, record data on transforming of existing rules and procedures which are used to evaluate performance and initiate action.

MOTIVATION

Motivation is the driving force by which humans achieve their goals. Motivation may be rooted in a basic need to minimize physical pain and maximize pleasure (Armstrong 2002). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation: Intrinsic motivation refers to motivation that is driven by an interest or enjoyment in the task itself, and exists within the individual rather than relying on any external pressure. Extrinsic motivation comes from outside of the individual. Common extrinsic motivation are:- Rewards like money, coercion and threat of punishment. Extrinsic motivation can be internalized by individuals if the task fits with their values and helps to fulfill their basic psychological needs (McCarthy 1994). Drives and desires can be described as deficiency or needs that activates behavior that aim at a certain goal. These originate from within the individual and may not require external stimuli to encourage the behavior. Basic behavior can be sparked by deficiencies such as hunger which motivates a person to seek food, desire for praise or approval which motivates a person to behave in a manner pleasing to others (Chandra 2006). Extrinsic motivation is simply what is done to or for people to motivate them for example, pay increase, praise, promotion and punishments.

Hangman (2005) observed that if we do something it will lead to another. People work for money. Drummond (2001) observed that people can be conditioned to act in certain ways if they are rewarded for behaving as required.

Training

Training is the process of increasing the knowledge and skills of employee for doing particular job. It is an organizational activity designed to create the thinking and behavior of people and enable them to do their jobs in more efficient manner. It implies imparting technical knowledge and manipulative skills of problem solving and positive attitudes and developing an individual in all aspects. Organizations make arrangement for the development of their staff so as to improve the efficiency of management and workers. Individual workers and organizations benefit from training through job satisfaction which gives an employee confidence in handling the job assigned to him, thus resulting to self esteem and job security which leads to commitment to the organization. Also reduces accidents, spoilage of machines, reduces complaints and brings about better use of resources and brings good interpersonal relationships (Bally, 2008)

Effective training minimizes learning costs, improves individual, team and corporate performance in terms of out-put, quality, speed and overall productivity. Training is the corner stone of sound management for it makes employees to be more effective and productive. Training is a widely accepted problem solving device. (Armstrong 2003).

Critical review

The management style of industry should support enhancement of productivity in the organization. Should communicate the need for good alignment in change practices, provide systematic risk assessment, ensure that the change policies are investigated thoroughly and ensure change considerations are given proper weight when designing systems of work (Armstrong 2006).

6. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The researcher conceptualized the relationships, diagrammatically between independent and dependent variables.

Independent variables

Intervening Variables

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher used descriptive design in this study and targeted the employees and managers of livestock department in Nakuru County- Kenya. This comprised of 124 Members.

The study applied stratified random sampling procedure to pick 62 respondents.

According to Tabachnick and Fidel 2001 sample size is obtained using the formula;-

$$\frac{a \times c}{b} = z$$

Where a = Number of employees in each department/section

b = Total target population

C = sample size

Z = Number of respondents

Category	Target population	Percentage	Sample	percentage
Top management	5	4	2	5
Middle/lower mgt	13	10	7	13
Employees	106	86	53	86
Totals	124	100	62	100

Source: Researcher 2018

The research used primary data which was collected by use of questionnaire.

The instruments for data collection were validated and reliability tested at cronbach’s alpha 0.905.

Data analysis

The collected data was edited and coded to facilitate tabulation. The data was quantitatively analyzed using SPSS Program.

8. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Response Rate

62 respondents were administered with questionnaires but the 51 responded. This was 82% response rate.

Response on highest level of education

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Secondary	11	22
College	16	31
University	19	37
others	5	10
Total	51	100

Authors source (2018)

The study showed that majority of respondent (68%) had attained college and above levels of education.

Length of service

Category	frequency	Percentage
2 years and below	9	18
3 – 5 years	16	31
6 - 9 years	14	27
10 and above years	12	24
Total	51	100

Source: Researcher 2018

The study showed that majority of respondents (58%) had 3 to 9 years of service and 24 % had served the organization for ten years and above only 18% of the respondents served the organization for less than three years.

Effects of management style on employees' productivity

Category	frequency	Percentage
Very high	14	27
High	19	37
average	11	22
low	7	14
Total	51	100

Source: researcher 2018.

The study showed that the majority of respondents (64%) felt that management style affects to a greater extend the productivity of employees. Only 14% of the respondents felt that management style has no effect on employees' productivity.

Motivation

Effects of motivation on employees' productivity

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	17	33
High	19	37
Average	9	18
Low	6	12
Total	51	100

Source: researcher 2018.

The study showed that the majority of respondents (81%) felt that motivation affect greatly the productivity of employees. Only 12% of the respondents felt that motivation does not affect employees' productivity.

Staff Training

Effect of staff training on employees' productivity,

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	18	35
high	22	43
Low	11	22
Total	51	100

Source: researcher 2018.

The study has shown that training affects greatly employees' productivity. 78% of the total respondents indicated that training affect greatly the productivity of employees. Only 22% of the respondents felt that

training had low effect on employees' productivity in their organization.

9. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Management style and employee productivity

57% of the respondents indicated that management style in livestock department affected their productivity. Therefore the style of management that a manager uses affects the productivity of his employees.

Motivation

The study found strong correlation between motivation and employees' performance in livestock department Nakuru County. 81% of the total respondents indicated that motivation in their organization affected greatly their productivity. Therefore managers should enhance employee motivation in their organization since it indices employees to work more, thus high employee productivity.

Training

The study found training being very effective in enhancing employees' productivity. 78% of the total respondents reported high influence of training to their productivity.

10. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the organization that builds its culture on good management style, employees' motivation and employees training gains a competitive edge over its competitors since these enhance employees' performance thus high organizational productivity. Trained employee has confidence and skills to perform his tasks, motivated employee commits himself fully to meeting goals of the organization and good leadership provides direction to the employees and wins employee's willing corporation. This kind of culture provides a conducive work environment for the employees.

REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, M. (2003),. Human Resource management practices 9th edition, London, UK: Kogan Page ltd
2. Appley, R. (2003). Modern Business Administration and Finance (3rd Edition), New York, NY: Prentice

3. Bally, D (2008) Procurement Principles and management (5th edition), New york, NY: Prentice Hall.
4. Chopra,S. & Clara, S (2004), Supply chain management(2nd edition), New Jersey, USA: Prentice Hall.
5. Cooper, R. D & Schindlers, P. (2003). Business Research Methods (8thedition) New York, NY: Tata McGraw Hill.
6. Dickson, P. (2000), Cost Management (4th edition) New York, NY: Harcourt Brace College Publishers.
7. Drummond, G. (2001), New Product Development (4th Edition), New York, NY: Amcon Publishers.
8. Hangman, T (2005), Management concept and practices (4th edition), New York NY: Prentice Hall
9. Kothari, M. (2001) Research Techniques (2nd edition) New York NY: Pearson Publishers
10. Kothari, C.R. (2004). Research Methodology (4th edition), New Delhi, India: New Age International (p) ltd
11. Saleemi, N.A (2010), Practice of management (East Africa Edition) Saleemi publishers

